

success story

> **Pilot 2:
Sustainable
Agriculture
National scale**

Carbon Monitoring System for Lithuanian Soils

Climate change and anthropogenic pressures have been reducing the agricultural land sink over the last several decades. The European Union (EU) has recently created significant policies and incentive regulations to promote sustainable land management practices, such as the 2030 climate target plan, the new Forest Strategy, the new Common Agricultural Policy Regulation (CAP), 2023-2027, and the amendment of the Regulation (EC) 2018/841 on LULUCF. In that regard, EU-level incentives encourage growers to adopt Carbon (C) farming approaches (e.g., sustainable soil management practices, cover crops) to increase C. However, the effectiveness of C farming is largely influenced by uncontrolled climate factors (e.g., precipitation, temperature, solar radiation), nutrients availability, and land management practices (e.g., reduced tillage).

Tapping into the current enormous source of reliable and wide-spread spaceborne data and integrating them in cloud-based infrastructures using data analytics and AI applications, EIFFEL's Pilot 2 provides an answer to the issue of data limitation to scale, and transform into digital, the monitoring and reporting capacities from farm to regional datasets having the desired spatio-temporal representativeness and reliability.

Interbalkan Environment Center develop AI-enhanced digital-based tools and services supported by open-source data for large-scale and efficient monitoring of parameters and proxies to support C stocks assessment in croplands. The parcel level resolution of the products serves the end user needs (Lithuanian Paying Agency) for the rational implementation of the new-CAP and eco-schemes.

Figure 1 SOC and clay content maps with Pixel-based (10m), uncertainty and parcel level predictions.

For more products, please visit our website (WP5/Task 5.2):

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/what-we-do>

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

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